

Studies in the Synthesis of Furocoumarins : Part VIII.* Synthesis of Alkylpsoralenes and Alkyl Isopsoralenes

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Claisen rearrangement of 7-allyloxy-4-phenyl-8-methylcoumarin gave 7-hydroxy-6-allyl-4-phenyl-8-methylcoumarin which was converted to 5',8-dimethyl-4-phenyl-psoralene by first treating it with sulphuric acid followed by dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal. 4-Phenyl-8-methylpsoralene was synthesised by subjecting 6-allyl derivative to ozonolysis followed by cyclisation with *o*-phosphoric acid. (IVa) and (IVb) were similarly synthesised from 7-hydroxy-8-allyl-3-phenylcoumarin and 7-hydroxy-8-allyl-4-methylcoumarin respectively. 5-Allyloxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin on Claisen rearrangement gave (VI) and not (V), the structure of (VI) was revised on the basis of NMR Spectra. (VI) on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal gave (VII).

In recent years, the importance of *o*-hydroxy allyl coumarins has been increased because of the fact that these can be used as starting materials for the synthesis of 2-substituted furocoumarins¹ as well as unsubstituted furo coumarins² which occur in nature. In continuation of our previous work on synthetic furocoumarins, we report here the synthesis of both types of furocoumarins starting with suitably substituted *o*-hydroxy allylcoumarins.

7-Hydroxy-8-methyl-4-phenylcoumarin was allylated with allylbromide, potassium carbonate and acetone to give 7-allyloxy-8-methyl-4-phenylcoumarin (Ia) which when subjected to Claisen rearrangement in dimethyl aniline afforded 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-6-allyl-4-phenylcoumarin (Ib). The cyclisation was carried out by triturating the 6-allyl derivative with concentrated sulphuric acid to give 5',8-dimethyl-4-phenyl dihydropsoralene which on dehydrogenation with Pd/C (10%) in refluxing diphenyl ether furnished 5',8-dimethyl-4-phenylpsoralene (IIa).

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| <p>1 a : R = -CH₂CH = CH₂; R₁ = H</p> <p>b : R = -H; R₁ = -CH₂CH = CH₂</p> <p>c : R = -H; R₁ = -CH₂CHO</p> | <p>II a : R = CH₃</p> <p>b : R = H</p> |
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* Part VII, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1970, **47**, 1058.

1. K. D. Kaufmann, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 117; and subsequent papers.
2. R. Aneja, S. K. Mukerji and T. R. Seshadri, *Tetrahedron*, 1958, **4**, 286.

The above 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-6-allyl-4-phenylcoumarin was subjected to ozonolysis whereby 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-4-phenyl-6-acetaldehydocoumarin (Ic) was obtained. This acetaldehyde derivative was cyclised by treating it with *o*-phosphoric acid to 8-methyl-4-phenylpsoralene (IIb).

3-Phenyl-7-hydroxycoumarin on allylation gave 7-allyloxy-3-phenylcoumarin (IIIa) which when subjected to Claisen rearrangement afforded 7-hydroxy-8-allyl-3-phenylcoumarin (IIIb). This when triturated with conc. sulphuric acid for 10 minutes gave 6-8-phenyl-2-methyl-5-oxo-5H-2,3-dihydrofuro(2,3-h)benzopyran derivative, which underwent dehydrogenation when refluxed with palladised charcoal (10%) in diphenyl ether to give 6-phenyl-2-methyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran (IVa).

7-Methyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran (IVb) was prepared by first subjecting 7-hydroxy-8-allyl-4-methylcoumarin to ozonolysis, followed by cyclisation of 7-hydroxy-8-acetaldehyde-4-methylcoumarin (IIIc) with *o*-phosphoric acid.

III

IV

- III a : $R = -C_6H_5$; $R_1 = R_2 = -H$; $R_3 = -CH_2CH = CH_2$
 b : $R = -C_6H_5$; $R_1 = R_2 = -H$; $R_3 = -CH_2CH = CH_2$
 c : $R = R_2 = -H$; $R_1 = -CH_3$; $R_3 = -CH_2CHO$

- IV a : $R = -C_6H_5$; $R_2 = -H$; $R_3 = -CH_3$
 b : $R = R_2 = -H$; $R_3 = CH_3$

Seshadri *et al.*, carried out Claisen rearrangement of 5-allyloxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin under different experimental conditions and obtained different products. When the rearrangement was carried out at 195–200°, a product which was insoluble in alkali was obtained and was assigned 4,7-dimethylcoumarino-5,6-chroman structure (V). When rearrangement of 5-allyloxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin was carried out at 160–5°, 6-allyl-5-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin was obtained. This on treatment with mercuric chloride gave an addition product which when treated with iodine in potassium iodide solution gave iodomethyl dihydrofuran derivative which when reduced with sodium and alcohol gave the product, m.p. 205–6°. The product was assigned 4,7-dimethylcoumarino- α -methyl-dihydrofuran (VI) structure. We subjected 5-allyloxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin to Claisen rearrangement by refluxing it in dimethyl aniline and also by heating it at 195–200° at atmospheric pressure and obtained the same product, m.p. 165° by both the processes. We have assigned 2,4,9-trimethyl-7-oxo-7H-2,3-dihydrofuro(2,3-f)benzopyran (VI) structure, on the basis

of NMR spectra. NMR spectra (CDCl_3) of (VI) showed the presence of three methyl groups as shown below :

Shift (δ)	Signals	Assignment
2.4	Singlet	3H, $-\text{CH}_3$ group at position 4
2.2	Singlet	3H, $-\text{CH}_3$ group at position 9
1.45	Doublet	3H, $-\text{CH}_3$ group at position 2

If it had the coumarino-chroman structure (V) as assigned by Seshadri *et al.*, it would have shown the presence of two methyl groups only. Further more, when (VI) was subjected to dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal (10%) in diphenyl ether it gave 2,4,9-trimethyl-7-oxo-7H furo(2,3-f)benzopyran (VII), m.p. 208° . This product was found to be identical with the product obtained by Seshadri *et al.* by first reacting 6-allyl-5-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin with mercuric chloride, followed by iodination and reduction with sodium and alcohol. Thus the revised structure of 4,7-dimethylcoumarino-5,6-chroman is 2,4,9-trimethyl-7-oxo-7H-2,3-dihydrofuro(2,3-f)benzopyran and the final product is 2,4,9-trimethyl-7-oxo-7H-furo(2,3-f)benzopyran and not 4,7-dimethylcoumarino- α -methyl dihydrofuran as assigned by Seshadri *et al.*

V)

VI

VII

EXPERIMENTAL

7-Allyloxy-8-methyl-4-phenylcoumarin (Ia) : 7-Hydroxy-8-methyl-4-phenylcoumarin (2.5 g.), allylbromide (1.5 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (15 g.) were refluxed in dry acetone for 5 hr. The acetone was evaporated and the residue was treated with water. The product was filtered, washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 119° . Yield 2.0 g. (Found : C, 77.62; H, 5.11%. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 78.08; H, 5.48%).

7-Hydroxy-8-methyl-6-allyl-4-phenylcoumarin (Ib) : 7-Allyloxy-8-methyl-4-phenylcoumarin (2 g.) was refluxed in dimethylaniline for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was poured in 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid. The product was filtered and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 157° . Yield 1.3 g. (Found : C, 77.73; H, 5.77. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 78.08; H, 5.48%).

4-Phenyl-5,8-dimethyl-4', 5'-dihydropсоралene : 7-Hydroxy-8-methyl-6-allyl-4-phenylcoumarin (1 g.) was triturated with conc. sulphuric acid for 5 mins. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice. The product was filtered and washed with very dilute sodium hydroxide solution and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 173°. Yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 77.90; H, 5.34. $C_{19}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.08; H, 5.48%).

4-Phenyl-5',8-dimethylpsoralene (IIa) : 4-Phenyl-5',8-dimethyl-4',5'-dihydropсоралene (0.5 g.) and Pd/C (10%; 0.3 g.) were refluxed in diphenyl ether (10 ml.) for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot. After cooling petroleum ether was added to the filtrate. The separated product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 170°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 78.74; H, 4.94. $C_{19}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 78.63; H, 4.71%).

7-Hydroxy-8-methyl-4-phenyl-6-acetaldehydecoumarin (Ic) : 7-Hydroxy-8-methyl-4-phenyl-6-allylcoumarin (1 g.) was dissolved in ethyl acetate (300 ml.). The solution was kept in freezing mixture and the ozonized oxygen was passed for 20 min. The reaction mixture was then subjected to hydrogenation using Pd/C (5%, 0.5 g.) as catalyst. The reaction mixture was filtered, solvent evaporated and residue was passed over alumina and finally crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 209°. Yield 0.7 g. (Found : C, 73.97; H, 4.63. $C_{18}H_{13}O_4$ requires C, 73.72; H, 4.44%).

4-Phenyl-8-methylpsoralene (IIb) : 7-Hydroxy-8-methyl-4-phenyl-6-acetaldehydecoumarin (0.5 g.) was heated with ortho-phosphoric acid (10 ml.) in a water bath for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice. The compound was filtered, washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and passed over alumina. It crystallised from benzene and petroleum ether, m.p. 190°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 77.98; H, 4.28. $C_{18}H_{12}O_3$ requires, C, 78.27; H, 4.38%).

7-Allyloxy-3-phenylcoumarin (IIIa) : 7-Hydroxy-3-phenylcoumarin (2.0 g.), allylchloride (1.4 g.), potassium iodide (2.5 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (9.0 g.) were refluxed in dry acetone (125 ml.) for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was worked as before and the compound crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 141°. Yield 1.7 g. (Found : 77.45; H, 4.78. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 77.71; H, 5.03%).

7-Hydroxy-8-allyl-3-phenylcoumarin (IIIb) : 7-Allyloxy-3-phenylcoumarin (1.8 g.) was heated in dimethylaniline (15 ml.) for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into 1 : 1 ice cold hydrochloric acid. The product was purified by taking it in sodium hydroxide solution. Filtrate on acidification gave the product which was further purified by passing it over alumina. Finally, it crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 170°. Yield 1.2 g. (Found : C, 77.31; H, 4.95. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 77.71; H, 5.03%).

6-Phenyl-2-methyl-5-oxo-5H-oxo(2,3-dihydrofuro 2,3-h)benzopyran : 7-Hydroxy-8-allyl-3-phenylcoumarin (1.0 g.) was triturated with conc. sulphuric acid. Working up as before the compound crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 165°. Yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 77.39; H, 4.93. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 77.71; H, 5.03%).

6-Phenyl-2-methyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran (IVa) : 6-Phenyl-2-methyl-5-oxo-5H-2,3-dihydrofuro(2,3-h)benzopyran (0.5 g.) and Pd/C (10%; 0.3 g.) were refluxed in diphenyl ether (10 ml.) for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as before and the

product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 155°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 78.65; H, 4.78. $C_{18}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 78.27; H, 4.35%).

7-Hydroxy-8-acetaldehydro-4-methylcoumarin (IIIc) : 7-Hydroxy-8-allyl-4-methylcoumarin (1 g.) was dissolved in ethyl acetate (200 ml.). The solution was then subjected to ozonolysis as before and finally the compound was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 181°. Yield 0.7 g. (Found : C, 65.83; H, 4.73. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.06; H, 4.59%).

7-Methyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran (IVb) : 7-Hydroxy-8-acetaldehydro-4-methylcoumarin (0.5 g.) was heated with ortho-phosphoric acid (10 ml.) in a water bath for 15 mins. Working up as before the compound was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 192°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found : C, 71.76; H, 3.80. $C_{12}H_8O_3$ requires C, 72.01; H, 4.00%).

2,4,9-Trimethyl-7-oxo-7H-2,3-dihydrofuro(2,3-f)benzopyran (VI) : 5-Allyloxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin (2 g.) was heated in dimethylaniline (15 ml.) for 4 hr. Working up as before, the compound crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 165°. Yield 1.8 g. The same product was also obtained when 5-allyloxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin was heated at 195–200° at atmospheric pressure. (Found : C, 73.24; H, 5.98. $C_{14}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 73.04; H, 6.00%).

2,4,9-Trimethyl-7-oxo-7H-furo(2,3-f)benzopyran (VII) : 2,4,9-Trimethyl-7-oxo-7H-dihydrofuro(2,3-f)benzopyran (0.5 g.) was subjected to dehydrogenation by refluxing it in diphenyl ether (15 ml.) and Pd/C (10%; 0.3 g.) for 5 hr. Working up as before the compound crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 209°. Yield 0.3 g. Mixed m.p. with the product obtained by first reacting 6-allyl-5-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin with mercuric chloride followed by iodination and reduction with sodium and alcohol, was not depressed. Yield 0.4 g. (Found : C, 73.47; H, 5.07. $C_{14}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 73.68; H, 5.27%).

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